

FINITE ELEMENT METHOD STUDY OF THE CRACK/CAVITY INTERACTION IN THE BI-MATERIALS

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to numerically analyze, using the finite element method (FEM), the effect of a spherical cavity located at the center of the interface between metal and ceramic materials, then at the metal level and finally at the ceramic level. The analysis focuses on evaluating the J-integral along the crack front as a function of the crack size and cavity diameter at the interface. Additionally, the study explores how the position of the defect relative to the interface and its location concerning the crack plane influences the stress distribution. Finite element simulations are performed to calculate the J-integral and the size of the plastic zone at a crack perpendicular to and terminating at a metal/alumina interface. This research provides valuable insights into the mechanical behavior of the interface, offering implications for the design and durability of bi-material structures.

Index Terms: Crack, Integral J, Von Mises Stress, Cavit, Bi-Material.

1. INTRODUCTION

The investigation of various factors, including the influence of loading conditions, the distance between the inclusion and the notch tip, the stiffness of the inclusion, and the distribution of Von Mises stress, as well as normal stresses (σ_{xx} and σ_{yy}). Additionally, a comparative analysis of different stress components is conducted.

The results indicate that the presence of an inclusion near the notch base significantly reduces both the size and shape of the plastic zone [1]. [2] examined the impact of inclusions in specific regions of bone cement, where loading conditions can induce crack opening, leading to crack propagation and, ultimately, aseptic loosening of total hip replacements (THR).

The results indicate that the highest stress concentrations occur around the sharp tip of the bony inclusion. Furthermore, the most critical cracks tend to form in the middle of the

cement mantle, particularly under one-leg standing load conditions during walking. The study of a crack originating from a cavity with a 0.7 mm diameter. The analysis considers two key parameters: the crack's position within the cement and the calculation of the stress intensity factor (SIF) in the proximal region of the orthopedic cement [3]. The investigation of a model femur fractures under quasi-static and dynamic loading to develop a digital simulation of fractures resulting from accidents.

This modeling will help enhance the design of transportation systems, improving passenger safety. To achieve this objective, a finite element method (FEM) simulation is conducted to analyze the mechanical behavior of the bone structure and predict femur fractures [4].

The study aims to reduce contact pressures and shear stresses at the stump-prosthetic interface to design a comfortable and well-fitted prosthesis for the patient. To achieve this, a finite element (FE) model of a trans-tibial prosthesis including the stump, socket, bone, and liner was developed to analyze and assess stress distribution at the stump-prosthetic interface [5].

The analyse of the fatigue behavior of an aluminum alloy plate with a central crack, subjected to tensile loading on its upper and lower edges. Several key parameters were examined, including the effect of loading with a load ratio of $R=0$.

The study investigates the influence of the load ratio on both repaired and unrepaired plates, where repairs were performed using two composite patches: boron/epoxy and graphite/epoxy.

Additionally, the impact of plate material on fatigue life was evaluated through a comparative analysis of different materials [6]. [7] analyzed the behavior of a crack in an aluminum plate under Mode I loading, both with and without reinforcement by a composite patch, using the finite element method (FEM). The results indicate that stress distribution under different loading conditions clearly demonstrates the effectiveness of composite patch repair.

The stress intensities significantly decrease in the reinforced plates compared to the unrepaired ones, highlighting the efficiency of the repair method. [8] analyzed the stress distribution in bone cement using a linear elastic approach. The evaluation focuses on Von Mises stress, normal stress, and shear stress as key criteria. The results reveal that the inclusion of residual stresses at the stem–cement interface leads to a notable increase in both Von Mises and normal stresses across different regions of the cement, compared to the case without residual stresses.

The investigation of the stress intensity factors (SIFs) under mixed-mode conditions during three activities: normal walking, climbing upstairs, and climbing downstairs. The results emphasize that a crack originating from a micro-interface under significant loading can lead to cement damage, ultimately contributing to prosthetic loosening. The stress intensity factors in Modes I, II and III are influenced by the orientation and location of the crack tip within the bone cement, with a 90° orientation resulting in significantly higher

values across all three modes. The study of the numerical simulation of a sub-interface crack in a limited permeable piezoelectric bi-material. The analysis ensures that both mechanical and dielectric equilibrium are satisfied by incorporating electrostatic tractions on the crack surface.

A crack-opening model is employed to integrate the crack face tractions within the framework of the extended finite element method (XFEM) [9]. [10] examined different crack orientations relative to the bi-material interface, including cracks parallel, perpendicular, and inclined to the interface.

The study also highlighted the effects of the mechanical properties of the joint materials, crack length, and metal thickness on the extent of the plastic zone and the J-integral at the crack tip. [11] used particle-reinforced composites (PRCs) are extensively in various engineering applications, yet interfacial fracture reliability remains a significant challenge that limits their further development.

To address this, the study combines the extended finite element method (XFEM) with a domain-independent interaction integral (DII-integral) method, which is developed to effectively evaluate the mixed-mode dynamic stress intensity factors (DSIFs) of an interface crack in bi-materials with an inclusion near the crack tip under impact loading.

The results provide insights that allow for the formulation of mathematical relationships describing the variation of the J-integral and plastic zone based on the crack position. Simulation of Bi-material interfacial cracks using the Element Free Galerkin Method (EFGM) and the Extended Finite Element Method (XFEM) under Mode I and mixed-mode loading conditions.

The results obtained from EFGM and XFEM for bi-material edge and center cracks are compared with those available in the literature. To verify the accuracy of the simulations, the results were obtained for two different Young's modulus ratios [12]. [13] focused on interface crack problems in piezoelectric bi-materials exhibiting k-class singularity.

The analysis uses a coupled finite element (FE) and extended element free Galerkin (XEFG) technique. Heaviside and asymptotic crack-tip functions are incorporated to capture the crack-tip singularity and discontinuities across the crack surfaces, allowing for local enrichment within the FE-XEFG framework.

This study aims to numerically investigate, using the finite element method (FEM), the impact of a spherical cavity positioned at three critical locations: the center of the metal–ceramic interface, within the metal, and within the ceramic.

The primary focus is the evaluation of the J-integral along the crack front as a function of both crack length and cavity diameter at the interface. Furthermore, the influence of the defect's position relative to the interface and its orientation with respect to the crack plane is examined in detail to understand its effect on stress distribution.

2. METHODOLOGY

The objective of this study is the numerical analysis, using the finite element method, of the effect of a spherical cavity located at the center of the interface. The analysis of the J-integral along the crack front is carried out as a function of the crack size and the cavity diameter at the interface. In other cases, this analysis conducted based on the position of this defect relative to the interface as well as its location concerning the crack plane. Finite element simulations conducted to calculate the J-integral and the size of the plastic zone at a crack perpendicular to and terminating at a metal/alumina interface. Figure 1 illustrates the geometric model of the cracked bi-material plate under Mode I loading.

The bi-material system consists of two bonded materials: alumina and metal, characterized by their respective mechanical properties:

Alumina: $E_c=345 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_c=0.3$ [1]

Metal: $E_m=72 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_m=0.33$ [1]

The ceramic exhibits a linear elastic behavior, whereas the metal follows an elastic-plastic behavior with a yield stress of $\sigma_y=300 \text{ MPa}$. The stress-strain curve of the metal is shown in Figure 2. The plate's geometric characteristics include a length H and width w such that $H=2w$, with $h_m=h_c=w/2$. An edge crack is considered perpendicular to the interface and located within the metal. Under an applied stress $\sigma_0=70 \text{ MPa}$, the crack may propagate toward the interface over a length h_m . The plate is subjected to a uniform tensile load distributed along the vertical (yy) direction with an amplitude of $\sigma_0=70 \text{ MPa}$. The numerical simulations were performed using the finite element code ABAQUS [14].

Figure 1: 3D geometric model of the bi-material showing a cavity at the interface

Figure 2: Stress-strain curve of metal

Figure 3: Mesh of the plate and near the crack

The plate modeled by 8-node isoperimetric quadratic elements. The crack tip singularity modeled by special elements as shown in Figure 3

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of cavity diameter

The first task is to study the interaction between a crack and a cavity located at the center of the bi-material interface within the crack plane (YOZ). To achieve this, we created a spherical cavity with different diameters (0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5) mm at the center of the interface. The analysis focuses on a crack originating in the metal and propagating toward the ceramic.

Figure 4: Variation of the J integral at the crack front as a function of the normalized distance for different crack lengths and for different cavity diameters

The effect of crack length and cavity size is shown in Figure III.4. This figure illustrates the variation of the J-integral as a function of four crack lengths $a = (5, 10, 15, 20)$ mm, along the crack front contour for different cavity diameters d_c . It is observed that the J-integral curve follows a linear trend in the intervals $[0, 0.1]$ and $[0.9, 1]$, whereas in the middle, it exhibits a parabolic shape. The analysis of these results reveals that, regardless of the crack and cavity sizes, the J-integral increases, reaches a maximum, and then decreases toward the specimen's edge. This maximum occurs at the mid-thickness (center) of the structure. The J-integral distribution along the crack front is symmetric concerning its center. It first reaches a peak, then decreases again, tending toward its minimum value. The J-integral values increase as both the crack length and cavity size grow. In fact, the highest J-integral values obtained for the largest crack and cavity sizes. Consequently, the mechanically stressed section is reduced, leading to an increase in stress and deformation at the crack tip. This increase characterizes the J-integral and the extent of the plastic zone. Thus, regardless of the crack position in the metal, the J-integral increases with the crack length. For a cavity size of $d_c = 5$ mm, the fracture energy at the crack tip increases significantly. This increase is more pronounced for a crack length of $a = 20$ mm. For small cracks, the J-integral remains low; however, beyond $a = 10$ mm, it grows rapidly with the crack length, reaching its maximum.

Von Mises Equivalent Stress

Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of Von Mises equivalent stress for four crack lengths, $a = (5, 10, 15, 20)$ mm and a cavity diameter of 5 mm. It is observed that the equivalent stress significantly exceeds the metal's yield strength $\sigma_y = 300$ MPa. In fact, the maximum

stress value is nearly twice the yield strength of the metal. This high stress concentration induces irreversible deformations, leading to the formation of a plastic zone in the immediate vicinity of the crack.

Figure 5: Contour of equivalent Von Mises stresses Metal / ceramic $a = (5, 10, 15, 20)$ mm

Figure 6: Max Von Mises equivalent stresses (MPa) as a function of crack length

Figure 6 illustrates the variation of the equivalent stress as a function of crack length. Indeed, we see that this stress increases proportionally with the crack length. They also note that the curves representing this relationship (as a function of the cavity diameter) have the same shape and are almost identical. However, they differ from each other beyond $a = 15$ mm.

Figure 7: Contour of Von Mises equivalent stresses (MPa)

The distribution of Von Mises equivalent stress (Figure 7) at the crack tip for $a=20$ mm and $d_c=5$ mm confirms the results presented in Figure 5. A significant stress amplification is observed around the cavity, which is directly linked to the fracture energy at the crack front. The equivalent stress considerably exceeds the metal's yield strength ($\sigma_y=300$ MPa). This high-stress concentration induces irreversible deformations, leading to the formation of a plastic zone within the metal and in the immediate vicinity of the crack front.

Effect of cavity position

Figure 8: Model of the bi-material with a cavity at the metal level

In this case, we will study the effect of the cavity's position, located in the metal near the interface, relative to the crack plane. To do this, we take the crack length $a = 20$ mm and the cavity diameter $d_c = 5$ mm. These dimensions are those for which significant values of the J integral were found in the previous study (influence of cavity size). The cavity is created at a height H_v : the distance between the center of the cavity and the crack plane.

Figure 10: Variation of the J-integral along the crack front for different cavity heights (H_v) in the metal

Figure 10 illustrates the variation of the J integral along the crack front for different cavity heights H_v . It can be seen that:

- All J values are greater than 0.
- The values of the J integral (in the center of the crack front) are greater than those at the ends.
- There is symmetry with respect to the center of the crack front.
- The J integral is inversely proportional to H_v , which implies that the closer the cavity is to the crack plane, the greater the risk of crack propagation.
- The highest value of the Rice integral: $J_{max} = 5.10 \text{ j/m}^2$ is obtained for a height $H_v = 5$ mm.
- The curves have the same shape and are almost identical, except for a height $H_v = 5$ mm

Effect of crack-cavity interaction at the ceramic level

Figure 11: Model of the bi-material presenting a cavity at the level of the ceramic
Influence of the position of the cavity, relative to the plane of the crack, on the J integral

Figure 12 represents the variation of the J integral along the crack front ($a=20\text{mm}$) in the ceramic for a cavity of diameter $d_c=5\text{mm}$ for different heights H_v (distance between the crack axis and the center of the cavity).

Figure 12: Variation of the J integral along the crack front for different cavity heights (H_v) in ceramics

4. CONCLUSION

The interaction between a crack and a cavity near the interface in bi-material systems is a critical phenomenon that can profoundly influence the mechanical performance and structural integrity of such materials. When a crack propagates in close proximity to a cavity located at the interface between two distinct materials, it often induces complex stress fields and deformation behaviors. The cavity, acting as a stress concentrator, alters the local stress distribution and can significantly affect the crack propagation trajectory. Variations in mechanical properties between the two materials and the cavity introduce pronounced stress and strain gradients, thereby modifying the driving forces for crack growth.

This crack–cavity interaction may lead to several detrimental effects, including premature crack initiation, accelerated crack growth, and a marked reduction in fracture toughness. Key parameters such as the cavity's size, geometry, and spatial position, as well as the mechanical contrast between the constituent materials, are critical in determining the severity of these effects. To accurately assess the durability and reliability of bi-material systems, it is essential to understand and characterize these interactions. Advanced numerical tools, particularly finite element analysis (FEA), offer robust capabilities for simulating and predicting the behavior of cracks in the presence of interfacial cavities. Such insights are instrumental in optimizing material design and enhancing the structural resilience of engineered components, thereby reducing the risk of early failure.

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